

Curriculum Implementation in Grades Eleven and Twelve at the Public Secondary School in Masbate City Divission

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Abstract:- The purpose of this study was to analyze the curriculum implementation in grades 11 and 12 at the public secondary school in Masbate City Division, during school year 2019-2020. Participants in the research endeavor were teachers in grades 11 and 12, principals, and assistant principals exclusively for the recommendations only. The actual number of respondents was one hundred thirty-three (133) of whom eleven (11) school heads and one hundred twenty-two (122) teachers. The data gathered was done through the distribution of survey questionnaires. The data gathered were treated using these statistical tools: frequency and percentage for the profile of teachers, weighted mean and rank order for the recommendations, to minimize the problems encountered by the teachers, improve and sustain curriculum implementation in grades 11 and 12. Majority of the respondents were on their late adulthood, most of them female, BSE graduates, Teacher I, had 5 teaching loads, and with satisfactory performance. Along teachers' preparation, curriculum enhancement, learning resources, they were competent. Material resources were the major problem of the senior high school teachers. School heads should provide relevant instructional materials and learning resources. Physical facilities, tools and science equipment be given preferential attention and forge partnership with the LGUs, NGOs and other government agencies for assistance. The practices of teachers on the initial implementation were generally competent but "very competent" along curriculum enhancement.

Keywords:- Implementation, Senior High School Program, Analysis, Masbate City.

I. INTRODUCTION

Each Filipino has a right to an excellent 12-year Basic Education curriculum under the improved K–12 Basic Education. This is in line with the 1992 Philippine Constitution's Article XIV, Section 2(1).

According to this law, it is the state's obligation and responsibility to establish, maintain, and support a comprehensive, adequate evaluation/assessment of the implementation of the grades 11 and 12 curriculum. Since evaluation/assessment is an integral part of the educative process, a teaching-learning cycle is not complete without the end results. Through this the teacher shall be able to appraise the senior high school students' performance as well as her own. And besides the effectiveness of the teaching and learning environment to include the technology used as tools,

the content, and the school program can also be judged through evaluation. The result of which is the potent source of information of the strengths and learning difficulties of students. Analyzing critically so as to determine the importance, value or significance of curriculum change, this would be the bases for recommendation to continue, discontinue or improve the senior high school program. A better "quality of education" is required in our nation. Setting the education sector as a top priority will help with this. Senior high school in the Philippines began in June 2016 thanks to the implementation of K–12 education made possible by Republic Act No. 10533. The K to 12 Philippine Basic Education Curriculum Framework strives to develop Filipinos "holistically" with 21st century abilities, hence it is crucial for the school to comprehend the underlying concepts of the program, especially senior high school, and the processes to follow in its execution.

The main objective was to analyze the curriculum implementation in the public secondary school in Masbate City Division, since its initial implementation in 2016-2017, hence this study.

II. METHODOLOGY

The study made use of the descriptive-analytical method of research. This method is designed on collecting and analyzing the data gathered. A questionnaire checklist was the main data gathering instrument. It was the researcher himself who personally distributed it to the targeted respondents. He has decided to have all the grades 11 and 12, teachers, the school heads and the assistant school heads for recommendations only of the eight (8) public secondary schools in Masbate City Division. Prior to the questionnaire distribution it was validated by a panel of experts and to ensure its reliability, a dry run was conducted by administering the instrument to the three secondary school head teacher III of the Province Division of Masbate. The researcher retrieved the accomplished instruments. The panel of the first dry run checked the instrument critically and found it in order that they answered the questionnaire with ease. So the researcher was advised to refrain from conducting a second dry run. The questionnaire has four parts: the respondent's profile, the practices of teachers during initial curriculum implementation, problems encountered by teachers, and recommendations offered by school heads and assistance. Considering that respondents were teachers, school heads and their assistants who were busy performing their respective task, the researcher had given a week to provide an authentic information needed in the survey questionnaire. After that the researcher went back to the eight

(8) secondary school for its retrieval.

The responses from the respondents were carefully collated, evaluated, and interpreted in order to draw conclusions. For the respondents' profile together with school heads recommendations were computed using the frequency and percentage. While average weighted mean was used to compute the practices of teachers in the initial curriculum implementation of the grades 11 and 12, problems encountered by respondents, and the researcher had used the following scales on the seriousness of these problems: Very Serious, 4 (scale from 3.50 – 4.00) ; Serious, 3 (scale from 2.50 – 3.49); Moderately Serious, 2 (scale from 1.50 – 2.49); and Less Serious, 1 (scale from 0.01- 1.49).

In the Division of Masbate City there are only eight (8) public secondary schools and one of these schools is an Integrated School. Two of the schools are situated in the City proper and the other six (6) schools are located in the remote barangays. Masbate National Comprehensive High School (MNCHS) is within the city. This is second biggest secondary school in the entire Bicol region had seventy-one (71) senior high school teachers. Nursery High School in Brgy. Nursery is three (3) kilometers from the City proper had eight (8) senior high school teachers. Usab High School is twelve (12) kilometers from the city proper had eight (8) senior high school teachers. Capitolina O. Legaspi Memorial National High School situated at Brgy. Malinta and it is fourteen (14) kilometers away from the city proper had thirteen (13) senior high school teachers. Alejandro delos Reyes High School at

Brgy. Cagay is nineteen (19) kilometers distance from the city had six senior high school teachers. All these four (4) secondary schools belonged to Masbate City south district one (1) and two (2). Bayombon High School at Brgy. Bayombon is seventeen (17) kilometers away from the city proper had seven (7) senior high school teachers. Bantigue High School at Brgy. Bantigue is seventeen (17) kilometers distance from the city proper, yet it can be reached through the use of motorized banca passing through the Masbate City Bay and the last secondary school is Bolo High School is more or less twenty-one (21) kilometers from the city proper. This can be reached by using either land and sea transportation had eight (8) senior high school teachers. These three secondary schools belonged to Masbate City North Districts one (1) and two (2). Every secondary school is managed by one (1) school head except MNCHS which is managed by a Principal IV and three (3) assistant principal II. All the secondary schools had a total number of one hundred twenty-two (122) senior high school teachers who answered the research problems one (1) to four (4). While the eleven (11) school heads answered only problem number four which was the recommendations to be offered. So the research study had an over-all respondents of one hundred thirty-three (133), considering the accessibility of the secondary schools in the City Division, the researcher did not experience difficulty in the distribution and retrieval of the questionnaires. It was for this reason that in order to get a reliable data, the researcher had decided to include all grades 11 and 12 teachers and school heads.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Profile on Age of Grades 11 and 12

Age Profile	Frequency	Percentage
60 and above	11	9.01
55 – 59	8	6.55
50 – 54	15	12.29
45 – 49	13	10.65
40 – 44	33	27.04
35 – 39	29	23.77
30 – 34	11	9.06
29 below	2	1.63
Total	122	100.00

A. Age:

Table 1 indicates the age profile of the grades 11 and 12 teachers. It includes frequency and percentage. As indicated in the table, out of one hundred twenty-two teachers eleven or 9.01 percent were 60 years old and above; eight or 6.55 percent belonged to 55-59 age bracket; fifteen or 12.29 percent of the teachers belonged to the age bracket of 50-54; thirteen or 10.65 percent belonged to the age bracket of 45-49; thirty-three or 27.04 percent belonged to the age bracket of 40-44; twenty-nine or 23.77 percent belonged to the age bracket of 35-39; eleven or 9.06 percent belonged to the age bracket of 30-34; and two or 1.63 percent belonged to the age bracket of 29 years old below.

The finding implies that majority of the senior high school teachers were matured enough. They were in their late adulthood. An individual who grow old in their profession was presumed that they performed better and gave their best that they can do especially teaching the senior highschool classes.

Table 2: Profile on Sex of the Grades 11 and 12 Teachers

Sex Profile	Frequency	Percentage
Male	40	32.79
Female	82	67.21
Total	122	100

B. Sex

This table shows the sex profile of Teachers -respondents. it includes frequency and percentage. As shown in the table, out of one hundred twenty-two teachers, 40 or 32.79 percent were males, and eighty-two or 67.21 percent were females. Majority of these teachers were females; for them teaching

was best where there was no hard work, no heavy objects to lift and besides they considered classroom as their home, taking care of children, unlike male teachers who were less in number. Most of them want to find job where they showed their prowess and masculinity, they prefer to work as military, engineers, and in the field of professions other than teaching.

Table 3: Profile on Educational Attainment Grades 11 and 12 Teachers

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
1. M.A. Graduate	10	8.20
2. M.A. CAR	30	24.59
3. BSE Graduate	44	36.07
4. Baccalaureate	38	31.14
Total	122	100

C. Educational Attainment

Table 3 reflects the educational attainment profile of senior high school teachers. The table includes the frequency and percentage. As reflected in the table of the one hundred twenty-two senior high school teachers only ten or 8.20 percent were M.A. graduates; thirty or 24.59 percent were M.A. CAR; forty-four or 36.07 were BSE graduates and thirty-eight or 31.14 were Baccalaureate degrees.

Based on the findings majority of the senior high school teachers were BSE graduates, and only very few were M.A. graduates out of the total frequency of respondents.

This implies that there is a need to require teachers to pursue their graduate studies, since they were teaching in senior high school classes. Teachers should be fully equipped with teaching competencies and skills on different disciplines. Teachers have to update, enhance and develop in order to catch up with skills in the new curriculum.

Table 4: Profile on Position title of Grades 11 and 12 Teachers

Position Title	Frequency	Percentage
1. Teacher I	54	44.26
2. Teacher II	41	33.60
3. Teacher III	13	10.66
4. Master Teacher I	10	8.20
5. Master Teacher II	4	3.28
Total	122	100

D. Position Title

Table 4 indicates the position title profile of grades 11 and 12 teachers. It includes frequency and percentage. As indicated in the table out of one hundred twenty-two senior high school teachers, fifty-four or 44.26 percent were Teacher I; forty-one or 33.60 percent were Teacher II; thirteen or 10.66 percent were Teacher III; ten or 8.20 percent were Master Teacher I; and only four or 3.28 percent were Master Teacher II.

The finding implies that there was a great need of the school heads to move on and motivate their teachers to take their best foot forward to raise their position title to the next higher level from Teacher I to Teacher II, III and Master Teacher.

Teachers should not wait for the school heads to push them, but they too should be conscious of raising themselves.

Table 5: The Number of Teaching Loads of Grades 11 and 12 Teachers

Number of Teaching Loads	Frequency	Percentage
1. Five teaching loads with advisory class	41	33.60
2. Six teaching loads – no advisory class	26	21.31
3. Four teaching loads with advisory class	38	31.15
4. Four teaching loads with special assignment (subject coordinator)	8	6.56
5. Four teaching loads (in charge of the school canteen)	9	7.38
Total	122	100

E. Number of Teaching Loads

Table 5 indicates the number of teaching loads of the one hundred twenty-two senior high school teachers. The table includes the frequency and percentage. As indicated in the table, out of one hundred twenty-two senior high school teachers forty-one or 33.60 percent had five teaching loads with advisory class; twenty-six or 21.31 percent had six teaching loads without advisory class; thirty-eight or 31.15 percent had four teaching loads with advisory class; eight or 6.56 percent senior high school teachers had four teaching loads with special assignment as subject coordinators; nine or 7.38 percent had four teaching loads and assigned as in charge of the school canteen.

The finding implies that there was a need for additional senior high school teachers, because the researcher noted that there were over loading of teaching, and besides they were teaching the subject not their specialization. Teachers with five teaching loads with advisory class cannot focus on classroom teaching, less teaching-learning process occur. So, school heads accept the unqualified eligible teachers deployed by the Schools Division Office, and then the senior high school students suffer the consequences, especially those deployed teachers to teach the core subjects (English, Math, Science and Filipino).

Table 6: Profile on Performance Ratings of Grades 11 and 12 Teachers

Performance Ratings	Frequency	Percentage
1. Outstanding (O)	31	25.41
2. Very Satisfactory (VS)	46	37.71
3. Satisfactory (S)	28	22.95
4. Needed Improvement (NI)	17	13.93
Total	122	100

F. Performance Ratings

Table 6 shows the performance ratings of grades 11 and 12 teachers last school year 2018-2019. The table includes the frequency and percentage. As shown in the table out of one hundred twenty-two of grades 11 and 12 teachers, thirty-one or 25.41 percent had “outstanding” performance ratings; forty-six or 37.71 percent had a “very satisfactory” performance ratings; twenty-eight or 22.95 percent had a “satisfactory” performance ratings; seventeen or 13.93 percent of these teachers in Masbate City Division “needed

improvement”. These groups of teachers that needed improvement were those teachers deployed by the Schools Division Office who were not eligible and did not possessed the necessary qualifications, needed by the school, but due to lack of qualified applicants, they were accommodated. Those outstanding teachers were aspirants to any position higher than their present rank. The school heads should motivate their teachers to improve their performance since this is one of the criteria needed in any promotion.

Table 7: Teachers’ Practices on the Initial Implementation

Teachers’ Practices of	Average Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. Along Teachers’ Preparation	3.42	Competent	1
2. Along Curriculum Enhancement	3.01	Competent	3
3. Along Learning Resources	3.19	Competent	2
Grand Weighted Mean	3.21	Competent	

Table 7 shows Teachers’ practices on the initial implementation of grades 11 and 12 Curriculum It includes the computed average weighted mean, interpretation and rank.

As shown in the table, the practices of teachers were given according to rank. Rank 3 was along curriculum enhancement, had an average weighted mean of 3.01 interpreted as “competent”. Rank 1 was along the teachers’ preparation had an average weighted mean of 3.42 interpreted

as “competent” and Rank 2 was along the learning resources, had an average weighted mean of 3.19 interpreted as “competent” The findings explicitly implied that the practices of grades 11 and 12 teachers need improvement especially on the learning resources, more specifically on the provision of varied enhancement activities through computer lessons and TV viewing activities in teaching Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS).

Table 8: Problems Encountered by Grades 11 and 12 Teachers

Problems Encountered	Average Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. Along human resources	3.32	Serious	2
2. Along material resources	3.72	Very serious	1
Grand Weighted Mean	3.52	Very serious	

Table 8 reflects the problems encountered by grades 11 and 12 teachers. It includes the average mean, the interpretation and rank. As indicated in the table, material resources were the major problem of grades 11 and 12 teachers had an average mean of 3.72 interpreted as “very

serious” problem, Rank 1, and human resources had an average mean of 3.32 interpreted as “serious”.

The grand weighted mean was 3.52 interpreted as “very serious”. The solution of these problems should be prioritized

by school head if maximum improvement is to be desired.

Table 9: Recommendations can School Heads and Teachers Offer

Recommendations	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
1. School heads should prioritize the learning resources of the grades 11 and 12	133	100	1
2. Provides teachers with more instructional materials.	132	99	2
3. Improve the physical facilities of the school to attract learners and avoid absences and dropouts	131	98.5	3
4. Quality and honest assessment of grades 11 and 12 teachers	128	96.24	6
5. Classroom observation be made twice a week to check the current approaches used in teaching	127	95.49	7
6. Provides every classroom computers sets and TV sets for teachers and students in the classroom	126	94.74	8
7. Require teachers to have demonstration return after attending trainings	125	93.98	9
8. Encourage parents to support their children’s school needs and attend parents forum	124	93.25	10
9. Require teacher to use the pedagogical approaches in teaching	130	97.74	4
10. Require grades 11 and 12 teachers to push through with their graduate studies	129	96.99	5

Table 9 shows recommendations offered by school heads and teachers to improve the grades 11 and 12 curriculum. The following recommendations were made, as can be seen in the table: 1) school heads should prioritize the learning resources of the grades 11 and 12 classes had a frequency of one hundred thirty-three or 100 percent rank 1, 2) provide teachers more instructional materials, had a frequency of one hundred thirty-two or 99 percent, rank 2, 3) improve the physical facilities of the school to attract learners and avoid absences and drop-outs, had a frequency of one hundred thirty-one or 98.5 percent, rank 3, 4) quality and honest assessment of grades 11 and 12 teachers had a frequency of one hundred twenty-eight or 96.24 percent, rank 6; 5) classroom observations be made twice a week to check the current approaches used in teaching in grades 11 and 12 classes had a frequency of one hundred twenty-seven or 95.49 percent, rank 7; 6) provide every classroom computer sets and TV sets for teachers and students in the classroom had a frequency of one hundred twenty-six or 94.74 percent, rank 8; 7) require teachers to have a demonstration returns after attending trainings had a frequency of one hundred twenty-five or 93.98 percent rank 9; 8) encourage parents to support their children’s school needs and attend parents forum, had a frequency of one hundred twenty-four or 93.25 percent, rank 10; 9) require teachers to use the pedagogical approaches in teaching, had a frequency of one hundred thirty or 97.74 percent rank 4; and 10) require teacher to push through their graduate studies (to improve oneself is to grow professionally while in service, asides from attending INSET/seminars) had a frequency of one hundred twenty-nine or 96.99 percent rank 5. All these recommendations if implemented will enhance the learners’ academic performance together with the teachers and school performance as a whole.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In light of the results the conclusions were deduced: Most senior high school teachers were 40-44 years old, females, BSE graduates, Teacher I, with five teaching loads with advisory class and had a very satisfactory performance rating. Practices of teachers in the initial implementation of grades 11 and 12 curriculum were “very competent” along teachers’ preparation grades 11 and 12 teachers encountered “very serious” problems along material resources but serious along human resources. Recommendations when implemented will improve the curriculum.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

The conclusions resulted in the following recommendations: School heads should provide relevant instructional materials and learning resources. Physical facilities, tools, and Science equipment be given preferential attention. School heads should solicit the help of the Local Government Unit for an increase of local funds. Require grades 11 and 12 teachers to grow professionally.

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